

Whole-genome assembly of four plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria isolated from alfalfa and wheat rhizospheres in Tunisia

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Abstract

Soil salinization is a widespread abiotic stress that negatively affects agricultural productivity, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions, highlighting the importance of isolating new bacterial strains as potential resources for improving plant performance under stress conditions. In this study, four bacterial strains were isolated from the rhizosphere of alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*) and wheat (*Triticum aestivum*) plants cultivated in agricultural soils in Tunisia. These isolates are of interest due to their potential as plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR), with implications for enhancing plant growth, improving nutrient availability, and increasing tolerance to abiotic stresses in agricultural systems. Here, we report high-quality whole-genome sequences of strains Sp405, Sp408, Sp307_1, and Sp310 obtained using Illumina paired-end sequencing technology. Genome-based taxonomic analysis identified the isolates as *Bacillus halotolerans* (Sp405 and Sp310), *Bacillus paralicheniformis* (Sp307_1), and *Serratia liquefaciens* (Sp408). The resulting assemblies comprised (14–45) contigs (≥ 1000 bp), with genome sizes ranging from 4.07 to 4.85 Mb. These

genomic resources provide valuable insights into the genetic potential of rhizosphere-associated bacteria and support future investigations into the molecular mechanisms underlying plant–microbe interactions and their application in sustainable agriculture.

Keywords: whole-genome sequencing, WGS, PGPR, rhizobacteria, *Bacillus*, *Serratia*, wheat, alfalfa, Tunisia, salinity stress, drought stress

1. Introduction

The rapid growth of the global population represents a major challenge for food security, requiring a significant increase in agricultural productivity. However, climate change has exacerbated the impact of abiotic stresses, particularly drought and soil salinity, which are among the most critical constraints limiting crop yields worldwide. These stresses are especially severe in Mediterranean regions, including Tunisia, where arid and semi-arid climates, irregular rainfall, and increasing soil salinization contribute to land degradation and reduced agricultural productivity (FAO 2021; IPCC 2022). In agreement with this, Liu et al. (2025) reported that drought and soil salinity are major abiotic stresses limiting crop productivity, particularly in arid and semi-arid regions.

From an ecological perspective, Tunisia presents a relevant context for studying these stress factors due to its pronounced bioclimatic gradient, ranging from Mediterranean conditions in the north to arid and desert environments in the south (You et al. 2016). In addition to abiotic stresses, agricultural productivity in Tunisia is also significantly constrained by biotic stress factors, including phytopathogens such as fungi, bacteria, viruses, and insect pests. These biological agents can directly reduce crop yield and quality, and their impact is often exacerbated under abiotic stress conditions, where plant defence mechanisms are weakened.

In this context, the use of plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria (PGPR) represents a sustainable alternative to chemical fertilizers and pesticides for mitigating both abiotic and biotic stresses in agricultural systems. Four PGPR strains were isolated from soil samples collected from the rhizospheres of different plants growing in arid regions of Tunisia. The strains were selected based on their plant growth-promoting (PGP) traits and their tolerance to salt stress. In the present study, we report the whole-genome sequencing (WGS) of these bacterial strains, which provides a more accurate taxonomic identification and a deeper insight into their genetic diversity. In addition, the genomic data generated will support the discovery of genes involved in plant–microbe interactions and stress tolerance, thereby facilitating their functional characterization and potential biotechnological valorization.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Bacterial strains

Strains Sp405 and Sp408 were isolated from alfalfa-growing soils affected by salinity and drought stress, with no fertilizer inputs, in the Mahres region (Sfax, Tunisia; 34°31'51.3"N, 10°31'11.7"E), while Sp307_1, and Sp310 were isolated from wheat rhizosphere soils in the Nabeul region (Tunisia; 36°28'20.8"N, 10°41'45.3"E).

2.2 Whole-genome sequencing and bioinformatic analysis

Whole-genome sequencing was performed on four PGPR bacterial strains by MicrobesNG (Birmingham, UK) using standardized protocols (<https://microbesng.com/>). For strain submissions, bacterial isolates were cultured and prepared according to MicrobesNG procedures prior to sequencing. Genomic DNA was extracted, quantified, and processed using an automated workflow.

Sequencing libraries were prepared using the Nextera XT Library Prep Kit (Illumina, San Diego, USA) following the manufacturer's instructions, with minor modifications including a two-fold increase in input DNA and an extended PCR elongation time of 45 seconds. Libraries were sequenced on an Illumina NovaSeq 6000 platform using a 250 bp paired-end strategy.

Raw sequencing reads were adapter-trimmed and quality-filtered using Trimmomatic v0.39 (Bolger et al., 2014) with a sliding window quality threshold of Q15. High-quality reads were assembled de novo using SPAdes v3.7 (Bankevich et al., 2012). Genome annotation was performed by MicrobesNG using Prokka v1.11 (Seemann, 2014) as part of their standard pipeline. All bioinformatic analyses were conducted using default parameters unless otherwise stated.

3. Results

3.1 Genomic properties

Whole-genome shotgun sequencing was performed on four bacterial isolates obtained from the rhizosphere of alfalfa (*Medicago sativa*) and wheat (*Triticum aestivum*). High-quality paired-end sequencing reads were generated for all isolates using the Illumina NovaSeq platform and deposited in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under accession numbers SRR38250564, SRR38264625, SRR38277372, and SRR38275184.

Genome assembly and submission to DDBJ/ENA/GenBank were successfully completed for four isolates, including Sp405 (*Bacillus halotolerans*), Sp408 (*Serratia liquefaciens*), Sp307_1 (*Bacillus paralicheniformis*), and Sp310 (*Bacillus halotolerans*), which have been processed and assigned accession numbers.

Assembly statistics varied among isolates, with contig numbers ranging from 14 to 45 (≥ 1000 bp), GC content between 43.6% and 56.4%, and sequencing coverage ranging from 52.6X to 113.3X. These data provide a comprehensive genomic resource for studying PGPR associated with alfalfa and wheat rhizospheres.

As shown in Table 1, the four rhizospheric bacterial isolates displayed notable variability in their genomic characteristics, with genome sizes ranging from 4.07 to 4.85 Mb and GC content between 43.64% and 56.39%. The number of contigs (14–24) and sequencing coverage (52.6X–113.3X) indicate differences in assembly completeness and quality, with some strains showing more contiguous and higher-coverage assemblies than others.

Table 1. Genomic features of the four strains isolated from the rhizosphere of plants in Tunisia.

	Alfalfa_Sp405	Alfalfa_Sp408	Wheat_Sp307_1	Wheat_Sp310
Strain ID	Sp405	Sp408	Sp307_1	Sp310
Source	Alfalfa rhizosphere	Alfalfa rhizosphere	Wheat rhizosphere	Wheat rhizosphere
Identification	<i>Bacillus halotolerans</i>	<i>Serratia liquefaciens</i>	<i>Bacillus paralicheniformis</i>	<i>Bacillus halotolerans</i>
BioSample	SAMN57446810	SAMN57469387	SAMN57491590	SAMN57485286
GenBan WGS	JBXXHZ000000000	JBXUFT000000000	JBXTZK000000000	JBXTZJ000000000
SRA accession	SRR38250564	SRR38264625	SRR38277372	SRR38275184
Genom size (bp)	4108400	4851303	4260812	4071325
GC content (%)	43.64	56.39	45.85	43.76
Mean coverage (X)	57.1892	113.341	75.86	52.6725
Number of reads	478982	1124476	659014	436792

3.2 Data availability

JBXXHZ000000000, **JBXUFT000000000**, **JBXTZK000000000**, and **JBXTZJ000000000**. The versions described in this paper are **JBXXHZ010000000**, **JBXUFT010000000**, **JBXTZK010000000**, and **JBXTZJ010000000**. Raw sequencing reads have been deposited in the NCBI Sequence Read Archive (SRA) under BioProject accession numbers

PRJNA1457109 and **PRJNA1457552**, with run accession numbers **SRR38250564**, **SRR38264625**, **SRR38277372**, and **SRR38275184**.

4. Statement on continuing work

These datasets are available prior to formal publication and should be considered preliminary. We welcome feedback from the community. For further information, please contact Ibtisem KHALIFA (ibtisemkhlifa@yahoo.com)

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